

Isotopic Exchange Reactions between Bromide and Bromate Ions in Aqueous Solution of Ammonium Bromide and Cadmium Bromate

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Though the isotopic exchange between Br^- and BrO_3^- in aqueous solution of the sodium and potassium salts is known to be extremely slow upto 200° , the finding that measurable exchange occurs if cadmium bromate is used suggested the need for a detailed study of the exchange kinetics with labelled Br^- and cadmium bromate for different concentrations of the latter and at different temperatures. A mechanism of the exchange is suggested.

Though isotopic exchange reactions between iodide-iodate¹⁻⁴, iodine-iodate^{1,5} and chlorine-chlorate⁶ have been studied extensively, the isotopic exchange reaction between bromide and bromate ions⁷ has been studied only to a limited extent. This is due to the very slow rate of exchange between bromide and bromate ions using the alkali bromates. We observed no isotope exchange between sodium bromide and sodium bromate upto about 200° .

Recently while working on the thermal annealing of chemical effects due to (n, γ) reactions in cadmium bromate Arnikar *et al.*⁸ observed almost cent per cent reformation of bromate by annealing at 150° . This unexpectedly high retention has been attributed by them to the occurrence in part of rapid isotopic exchange between bromide and bromate ions in the system.

In view of this interesting result of rapid exchange between bromide and bromate ions when the latter is associated with cadmium ion but not with alkali ions, the present study was undertaken to obtain kinetic data for the exchange over a wide range of reactant concentration and for two temperatures 125° and 150° .

EXPERIMENTAL

Cadmium bromate was prepared by allowing a solution of cadmium sulphate to boil with an excess of barium bromate for several hours. After the removal of the insoluble barium sulphate, the supernatant solution was concentrated when the less soluble barium

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bromate separated out and finally an impure cadmium bromate was allowed to crystallize. This was kept overnight at -20° after dissolving in a minimum quantity of water. At this temperature the solubility of barium bromate is only about 0.02%. Subsequent purification was done by repeated crystallizations.

A solution of labelled ammonium bromide was prepared by diluting the radioactive ^{82}Br as ammonium bromide without adding any inactive bromide. The molarity of the diluted solution was known from the data of specific activity and activity present in the parent solution as supplied by the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre.

In a series of pyrex tubes 5 ml of the reaction mixture were taken with the help of a hypodermic syringe and was hermetically sealed off. The sealed tubes were placed in an electronically controlled oil bath at the desired temperature held constant to within $\pm 2^{\circ}$ and the reaction was allowed to proceed. The tubes were taken out from the oil bath after different time intervals and immediately chilled to room temperature when the exchange equilibrium is frozen. The reaction mixture was then diluted to 10 ml and subjected to chemical analysis. The chemical separation of the bromide and the bromate was carried out by the method of Boyd *et al.*⁹ which is based on a rapid exchange between bromine and bromide. To the diluted solution of the reaction mixture 0.03 ml of pure bromine was added and the solution was allowed to stand for 10 minutes for complete exchange. This was next extracted with five equal volumes of extra-pure carbon tetrachloride making a total volume of 10 ml.

Activity measurements : The activities in the aqueous and organic layers were measured by a liquid G.M. counter. The exchange, defined as the ratio of the bromate activity to the total activity was calculated after correcting for the background activity. The reproducibility of individual observation of exchange was within $\pm 3\%$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The kinetics of the reaction have been studied under conditions of four concentrations of bromate ions ranging from 0.1M to 0.5M at 125° and 150° keeping the bromide concentration equal to 4×10^{-5} (fig. 1 to 4). In each of the above cases k the rate constant

FIG. 1

and the energy of activation of exchange were calculated (Table 1). Following are some of the important observations.

TABLE 1

*First order rate constants of isotopic exchange between Br^- and BrO_3^- .
(conc. of $Br^- = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$)*

Conc. of BrO_3^-	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		Energy of activation kcal mole
	125°	150°	
0.1 M	—	39.0	—
0.2 M	7.9	33.7	19.0
0.3 M	7.0	30.0	19.1
0.4 M	7.1	39.6	21.7
0.5 M	7.6	—	—

- (1) Over the concentration range of 0.2 to 0.4M of bromate at 125° the percentage exchange is found to vary from 13 to 65 respectively within 10 mins whereas the corresponding values at 150° are 83 and 97.

- (2) All the results agree with the general first order kinetics for the exchange rate and the rate constant k is independent of the concentrations of reactants.
- (3) A result of particular interest is that the exchange is almost cent per cent at 150° within 60 mins.

The rapid exchange with cadmium bromate leading to almost cent per cent exchange at 150°, reported for the first time here, in contrast to the nearly total absence of exchange in sodium or potassium bromate even at 200° suggests the participation of the cation in the rate determining step of the exchange reaction.

Following mechanism is proposed :

- (1) The formation of the complex $[\text{Cd}(\text{BrO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Br} \cdot \text{Br}]^{--}$ in which the cadmium has a co-ordination number six, is considered to be the rate determining step.

- (2) The complex breaks into

The complex $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ | \\ (*\text{Br} \text{ O} \text{ Br})^{--} \\ | \\ \text{O} \end{array}$ which leads to the exchange reaction is formed from the cadmium complex in the rate determining step in (1).

In the solution of alkali bromates such a complex formation is not possible and hence there is little or no exchange as observed.

The study with other bromates of transition elements which permit a similar complex formation is in progress.